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**Interaction between a live instrument
and the electronic part
on the example of accordion music
– the sound perception from the points of view
of the composer and performers**

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Chapter 1. Introduction

In the case of any auditory phenomenon, we can speak of its perception – broadly speaking, simply hearing the phenomenon is its perception. The human ear perceives the incoming sound wave as a change in air pressure, with the frequency of vibrations needing to fall within a specific range – generally, it is commonly accepted to be between 20 Hz and 20 kHz. However, this is a highly individual characteristic, dependent on many factors, including:

- age – as years go by, this range narrows, especially its upper limit, and the threshold of hearing for different frequency bands changes; for example, a statistically healthy teenager can comfortably perceive frequencies ranging from 30 Hz to 18 kHz, while with age, the upper limit decreases (to 14 - 15 kHz, and in the case of elderly individuals, to 12 kHz or less),
- health condition, especially conditions causing hearing loss, prolonged exposure to noise, which occurs in certain professions,
- gender - women generally perceive high frequencies more intensely,
- place of residence – individuals from large cities, experiencing daily noise, perceive sound differently from those living outside urban areas,
- individual characteristics, such as the shape of the outer ear, ear canal, head size, and shape, individual specialization, such as undergone auditory training, or engagement in professions where sound perception plays a crucial role.

It is important to emphasize that we do not hear every frequency equally well – especially high sounds seem quieter, and the same goes for the lowest ones. This is a characteristic stemming, on the one hand, from the structure of the ear itself, but, on the other hand, shaped in the process of evolution. It is generally accepted that we hear best in the range from 1 to 4 kHz, with the maximum occurring at 3 kHz. This is because this range encompasses the most significant information for us – warnings of potential threats that are not visible but audible, or primarily speech, the most important part of which falls within the range from 400 Hz to 4 kHz. Since we communicate largely verbally, the intelligibility of speech is crucial here. In the case of frequencies up to 2 kHz to 5 kHz, there is also a phenomenon of resonance of the air column in the external ear canal, which additionally improves hearing and understanding of speech. Therefore, it is not coincidental that we perceive as the most pleasant, most natural, those instruments, musical sounds, which predominantly fall within the range from 1 to 4 kHz. Returning to the starting point, we can identify the perception of the key properties of sound – such as its frequencies. Usually, we can distinguish two sounds of different pitches even if this difference is around 0.3%. This means that we will recognize sounds of frequencies 440 Hz and 441.32 Hz as different in pitch. This is, of course, a very individual matter, but generally, hearing two sounds of different pitches in quick succession, we will perceive them as slightly different. Another matter is the perception of sound loudness, where the minimum difference that most people can hear is around 1 dB – although it should be remembered that this also depends on the frequency of the sound. We also feel a difference in the timbre of sound when complex acoustic phenomena are involved, such as the sounds of various instruments – thus, we can talk about the perception of timbre, which affects the recognition of the source.

The above theoretical introduction serves to make us aware of how complex the process of sound perception is, and in a narrower and most interesting scope for us – the perception of music. This is because we are dealing with a cognitive process, integrally linked with other accompanying processes, such as the analysis of the music itself, comparing what we hear with our experiences and knowledge, associations and creating images under the influence of musical experiences (e.g., individual visualization in imagination), assessing aesthetic values, building emotions, etc. In this context, we can speak of apperception, which can be understood, for example, as its perception and analysis based on possessed knowledge, experience, or reception, understood as perception being a representative result for a specific historical period, geographical region, cultural origin, etc. The perception of music has been a very significant part of research on music and psychoacoustic phenomena since the late 19th century. They focus on many aspects, such as the aforementioned broadly understood perception of sound and its parameters, elements of musical works, to psychoaesthetic phenomena. There is no doubt that the perception of music is a very individual phenomenon, dependent on personal characteristics, acquired

experiences, but also subjective feelings regarding aesthetic matters (in other words, taste). It is also different for individuals professionally involved in music, such as composers, musicians, producers, sound engineers, music critics (although for each of these professional groups, distinct differences can also be indicated) - and different for listeners, for whom it is simply a hobby, a way of spending free time. In the following part, we will focus on the phenomenon of sound and music perception by three participants of the event: the musician/performer, the composer, and the listener. And although opinions on this matter vary, it probably will not be a mistake to assume that ultimately the most important person here is the listener, the recipient of the musical work, for whom experiencing it should provide the greatest pleasure, aesthetic experiences, or positive emotions. The final success is thus a result of the efforts of the composer of the work and its direct performer(s).

Chapter 2. The Accordion as a Model Example of Differences in Sound Perception of an Instrument

The theoretical introduction aimed to prepare us for more detailed considerations regarding perception in the case of compositions involving two component layers – the electronic layer (which can be a pre-recorded audio file, material performed live, or a combination of both) and playing on an acoustic instrument. If we were to indicate one specific example of such an instrument that would very well illustrate the topic we are addressing, a very good choice would be the accordion. This is what we will focus on in the following part. Why the accordion? Of course, an analysis of the research subject can be conducted using other instruments, however, the accordion offers us a range of interesting possibilities. Firstly, due to its properties. The accordion is an instrument with a very rich sound, relatively large dynamics, and one whose sound covers almost the entire audible range. The lowest sound, the note E bass, corresponds to a frequency of 41.20 Hz, while the highest ones can have fundamental frequencies of 3520 Hz (A4), or even 4435 Hz (C#5) – of course, we must remember about overtones, so in the case of the note A4, for example, the fourth harmonic will have a frequency of 14080 Hz, for C#5 it will be 17740 Hz, thus many people may not even hear it. The character of the accordion's sound is primarily determined by the reeds with reed blocks, but also, in the next order, by the bellows, the body, and other elements. And finally, a particularly significant aspect for our considerations – it is an instrument in which we can notice a significant difference between the perception of its sound by the playing musician and the audience listening to it. Of course, when we talk about the simplest situation, that is, a strictly acoustic performance, without amplification. Let's pause here for a moment to consider the raised issue. As long as music was performed solely acoustically, that is, before the first microphones or loudspeakers were constructed, little attention was paid to the differences in the perception of sound by the musician and the listener. Such were the realities, and in fact, already from antiquity, places for staging performances or playing music were built, characterized by really good acoustics (one of the examples being Greek amphitheaters). If we take a closer look at a right-handed flutist, it becomes clear that during playing, the sound of the instrument is perceived much better by the musician's right ear, while for a listener sitting in the audience, the direction from which the same sound comes is perceived completely differently. The accordion is in this context an even more vivid example because it has two manuals and its tone is very spacious. Therefore, the accordionist – having a quite loud instrument right in front of them – feels a clear spatial separation of the manuals for the right and left hands, whose sounds come respectively from each side. This involves a series of phenomena that influence the brain's perception of the position of the sound source in space. In a large simplification, therefore, the sound from the left-hand manual reaches the left ear fractionally faster than the right one, and vice versa. Moreover, there is interaural level difference, and according to experts, the signals received by the ears slightly differ from each other in terms of high frequencies, due to attenuation introduced by the head and more strongly felt in the ear further from the source. Additionally, the sound wave reaches each ear at a different angle. These differences may be relatively small but are crucial for spatial orientation. It is worth noting that humans can easily recognize the direction from which a sound coming from the mid and high frequencies originates. It's more difficult with low frequencies. Other factors also influence the subjective perception of the sound reaching us, including reflections (contributing to echo and reverberation). If the time between the original sound and its reflection exceeds a certain value (usually it is said that this threshold is between 30 to 50 ms), then we

perceive them clearly as two sounds. If this time is shorter, our brain comes into play, and essentially uses only the beginning (the first sound) to locate the source in space. We have here the so-called Haas effect, sometimes also called the precedence effect.

If we now look at the listener's position relative to the accordionist on stage, it becomes immediately clear why the perception of his sound will be so different. The angle at which the sound wave reaches the recipient will be completely different, and there will be no significant difference between the two manuals, also any difference in distance to each will be marginal compared to the distance between the stage and the listener. In other words, the audience will not feel the spaciousness of the accordion's sound, the separation of manuals. The sound from the perspective of the listener will therefore have a point-like character, and will also be somewhat different in many respects – primarily, the distance from the source affects the decrease in intensity, which - simply put - is inversely proportional to the square of the distance from the source. Therefore, doubling the distance from the sound source will result in a fourfold decrease in intensity. However, this is a very general formula that does not take into account differences in attenuation depending on the frequency of the sound. Each acoustic environment is characterized by a specific attenuation curve, defining how the sound level changes depending on the frequency and distance. Generally, however, low frequencies travel the farthest distances, while the level of high frequencies decreases relatively fastest. In the case of a concert hall and typical distances between the stage and the audience, we usually do not have a situation where the sound in the rear rows differs so much from that in the front rows that it becomes problematic for the listener. Nevertheless, the perception of the instrument's sound by the musician and the listeners is very different. Also significant are the proportions with which the sound wave reaches the ears directly from the instrument and its reflections from the walls or elements of the concert hall decor. The musician hears a quite loud instrument close to them, whose sound slightly masks the delayed reflections - therefore, the tone seems much drier. From the perspective of the listener, the contribution of reflections is much greater, hence the subjective feeling of the instrument's tone enriched with reverberation. It should also be emphasized that these reflections can affect the perception of the timbre or articulation nuances. Therefore, it can be said for some simplification that the listener will hear not only the instrument itself but also the hall in which the concert takes place. The musician feels more various mechanical artifacts – in the case of the accordion, the operation of the bellows, the clatter of keys or buttons, etc. On the one hand, this is a strictly acoustic (i.e., physical) phenomenon, on the other hand, it is also psychoacoustic, resulting from a greater awareness of one's own instrument and knowledge of what contributes to its sound. Since we agree that the instrument is heard differently by the musician playing it and by the listener in the audience, and we already know why this happens, it is worth asking what practical significance this has and why we are even addressing this issue?

Chapter 3. The Issue of Sound Perception in Electroacoustic Music, Especially with the Involvement of Live Instruments

Contemporary music differs in many ways from ancient music. While not denying its roots, it has introduced many new elements that have changed the priorities of both composers and audiences. The catalyst for some of these changes has been technological advancement, while others relate to aesthetics, modes of listening, and so on. At the beginning of the 20th century, several tendencies began to emerge: a tendency to move away from tonality towards polytonality or even atonality, a change in approach to harmony, and a growing emphasis on rhythm. More importance was placed on the timbre of sound, making it a significant means of expression. Serious music also opened up to influences from folk traditions, drawing vitality and specific rhythms from them. However, these actions still largely involved traditional instrumental setups, instruments that had been known for centuries. Meanwhile, for several decades, there had been unprecedented technological progress. Many innovations became obsolete before they were even fully adopted, replaced by more advanced solutions. Artists increasingly began to realize that art – and therefore music – did not entirely correspond to the industrial era. This led to the emergence of electroacoustic music, which now constitutes a significant part of contemporary music, greatly influencing its aesthetics, narrative methods, and many other aspects. A particular type of electroacoustic music involves works written for a live, acoustic instrument and an electronic layer. Here, we focus on the

accordion, which we previously identified as an excellent example illustrating the entire issue. For various reasons, primarily its sound character and rich repertoire of extended performance techniques, it integrates exceptionally well with electronic sounds. It is also an excellent material for processing or transformation, even in real-time.

A separate issue concerns the often significant differences between the performance of ancient and contemporary music. In the latter, many elements come into play, such as the aforementioned extended performance techniques, a much greater emphasis on timbral control, precision in articulating details, strict adherence to timing, and sometimes even improvisation becomes an important element. The accordion is a particular case, as compared to other classical instruments; it seems relatively new, as its invention dates back to 1829. Moreover, it struggled to find its place in heavier genres of music, truly establishing itself only in the second half of the 20th century. This leads us to electroacoustic music involving the accordion. When we speak of the perception of its sound – both from the musician's and the listener's perspective – the instrument follows the same rules as any other acoustic instrument played alongside an electronic layer. The electronic layer fundamentally alters its perception, affecting aspects such as timbre, volume, articulation nuances, and more. Much depends on how dense this layer is and its importance in the piece; nevertheless, its presence influences perception. This brings us to the crux – the answer to why we are even addressing this issue. Since precision in performance is crucial in contemporary music, and the presence of an electronic layer fundamentally alters the perception of the instrument's sound, efforts should be made to align the perception by both the musician and the audience as much as possible. This ensures better control over the sound and provides necessary comfort for the performer, who will be aware that they are hearing essentially the same thing as the audience and can be certain that if every element sounds correct from their perspective, the same is true for the listeners.

Some musicians attempt to compare playing with electronics to having a band or orchestra, but it's an entirely different experience. There's no typical interaction, eye contact, or direct relationship between gesture and sound result when playing with a live performer. Even if a piece is written for a duet of accordion and synthesizer, it's a wholly different scenario. Several aspects are crucial here. Firstly, the electronic layer is heard through speakers; they, not the instruments, are the physical source of sound. Therefore, its location in space results from the composer's and sound engineer's actions, not from the position of any performer, even if virtual, on stage. Secondly, while the perception of the sound of the vast majority of acoustic instruments is determined by what happens primarily in the best heard frequency range (as mentioned in the introduction), the world of electronic sounds operates under entirely different rules. The composer can operate tones mainly in the upper range, extreme low basses, use contrasts, completely abstract and unrelated to anything known from nature or strictly acoustic world sounds. This abstractness, freedom in manipulating color, the ability to create the most unusual combinations from scratch, has always been the allure of electroacoustic music. As something entirely new, previously unknown. And though today we are literally surrounded by electronic sound, it is still perceived as something different from the known world of acoustic phenomena, abstract, atonal structures are still perceived as different from the familiar acoustic world. We could speculate on why this happens, but perhaps our hearing has evolved over thousands of years, while electroacoustic music has been around for less than 100 years. In any case, placing a familiar and naturally perceived instrument in an abstract, electronic context completely changes its perception.

Returning to the starting point – since in the case of performing electroacoustic music, we've deemed it desirable to strive for a unified perception of sound by the musician and the audience – what methods can achieve this, and how do they impact interpretational issues? It seems obvious that technology should be employed – specifically, appropriate microphone placement and amplification. Indeed, in the practice of electroacoustic music involving an acoustic instrument, it has become standard to amplify it. There are, of course, cases where such an instrument is left in its pure form without amplification, but this only makes sense when it's the composer's intention, and the juxtaposition of the acoustic instrument, whose sound emanates from a specific location, with the electronic sound serves a purpose, becoming an element of the piece. Otherwise, the audience experiences cognitive dissonance resulting from the inconsistency between these two elements. In the case of musicians who are just beginning to work with electronic material, there is sometimes a lack of understanding as to why their instrument is being amplified. They may think it's merely to make it louder, and while sometimes that's

necessary, the primary goal is to achieve a coherent connection between the acoustic and electronic elements so that they sound from the same speakers and are perceived as integral components of the musical work. For the accordion, amplification is particularly significant as it allows for the spatial rendering, placement in the sound panorama of the left and right-hand manuals – which is very attractive from the audience's perspective. Thus, the perception of such amplified accordion by the audience is very close to how the musician hears it. The only difference is that usually, the channels are reversed so that the audience, colloquially speaking, hears what they see. Since the accordionist typically faces the audience, although they hear the right-hand manual from the right side and the left-hand from the left, for the audience, the left side becomes the right and vice versa. From the perspective of proper perception, this is entirely correct – we see the musician play a specific part with their right hand, but for us, it comes from the left channel, so the sound is correct. The situation is slightly different when the musician is positioned sideways; in this case, there's more freedom, but a clear separation of the sound of both manuals always sounds good.

When we talk about the perception of pieces for a live instrument with electronics by the audience, amplification has a decidedly beneficial effect. But what does it look like from the musician's perspective? Here the matter is somewhat more complicated. For many classically trained instrumentalists who perform both historical and contemporary music, playing with amplification can pose a certain problem, especially at the beginning. They are accustomed to the pure, acoustic sound, and the fact that their instrument is also present in the amplification system can be troublesome, distracting, and worsen the performance comfort, etc. However, this is a matter of habituation and gaining experience, simply getting used to it. Over time, if they perform compositions involving electronics, they will appreciate amplification. At this point, it must be emphasized that the role of the sound engineer is very important, often performed by the composer himself. When we talk about the accordion, it is necessary to remember that it is quite a loud instrument, and from the musician's perspective, its acoustic tone will always dominate. If the composer's intention is to transfer precisely this natural character of the instrument to the amplification, proper microphone placement is crucial. The selection of appropriate instrumental microphones and their positioning – position, distance, or optimal capsule direction. In many cases, clip-on microphones attached to the instrument itself work well, but they also have their drawbacks, one of which is a tendency to transfer mechanical knocks – moreover, close-miking sometimes makes the sound less natural because it exposes certain frequency ranges. Here the accordion is particularly sensitive, although there are also microphones specially adapted for close sound pickup that transfer it in a very natural way. Stand-mounted microphones are safer in many respects and will also work better in repertoire involving extended playing techniques (e.g., percussion effects), but it should be borne in mind that the accordionist is constantly in motion, opening and closing the bellows, etc.

A separate case is when the composer's intention is not to reproduce the natural sound of the accordion, but rather to change it using electronic means, by adding effects or even a very radical transformation of the sound. It is very important for the performer to hear everything as well, to have control over the sound and full awareness of what is happening. This is very difficult because if the sound of the instrument is radically processed, the musician hears not only himself but also what the electronics do with his part. This means that he must divide his attention and be able to cooperate with electronics, which requires practice and experience. And also ear training. In such a situation, there are two options to consider – a properly selected stage monitor, in which the performer will hear himself with the accompaniment of electronics, or individual in-ear monitoring. Playing with headphones is a challenge for musicians because then they are isolated to their own instrument and hear it only through amplification, but this can also be mastered through practice. Let's add that in such a situation, the use of closed headphones is necessary, guaranteeing better separation and minimizing the risk of bleed (the penetration of the listened material into the microphones). Of course, in any case where we deal with an electronic layer, monitoring is necessary - whether in the form of stage monitors or headphones, so that at least the electronics themselves are present in it. And finally, a fairly common case, the necessity of playing with a metronome and a click signal – here you cannot avoid headphones, at least in one ear, which will significantly affect the perception of sound by the musician.

When addressing the issue of sound perception in electroacoustic music, attention must be paid to several other issues – primarily to the practically unprecedented precision in execution, which often

necessitates playing with a click, as without it, it is practically impossible to adhere so closely to the timeline. It is also helpful to place a monitor on stage displaying the time and possibly also the graphical representation of the electronic part's waveform. Much depends on the composition itself, how the electronic part is constructed. However, if a strict correlation between it and the instrumental part is crucial, then even minimal delays or too early playing of a specific sound can ruin the effect. In the case of strictly instrumental music, 100 ms is a completely negligible, imperceptible time, but in electroacoustic music, it is a quantity that can decide whether two sound events will synchronize or not. It is also necessary to consider the refractory period, which for most sounds falls within the range of 10 ms to 15 ms, although for the lower range and especially low tones, it can even be 100 ms. This is the time that elapses between the arrival of a specific auditory stimulus at the ears and its registration by the brain, becoming aware of what just happened. It may seem like very little, but in the performance practice of electroacoustic music, it can be significant. Therefore, the performer cannot follow the electronic layer but must anticipate it in their consciousness, knowing what will happen and react before the stimulus is perceived by their brain.

The second aspect worth mentioning is the practical implications of Weber-Fechner's law, which determines the relationship between the response of the biological system, in this case, hearing, to a given stimulus. Simplifying this, the biological system's reaction does not depend directly on the direct magnitude of the stimulus but on the relative change, or the difference between it and another stimulus, to be able to distinguish them. We can talk about the threshold of sensitivity, which determines the minimum difference in the intensity of a particular stimulus that we are able to register. Translating this into musical events, the perception of a specific sound does not depend directly on its pitch, volume, or timbre but on how much one of these features stands out against the background of other accompanying sounds. In other words, a specific sound can be perceived completely differently when it sounds in complete silence compared to when it is played during the playback of an intense electronic passage. Composers, sound engineers, and performers should primarily remember this when creating their works. However, this is a remark primarily addressed to the former, not to include parts in their compositions that have no chance of proper perception, whether by the performer or the listeners themselves. In the case of electroacoustic music, whose technical possibilities are practically unlimited today, the creator faces a completely new problem - the human auditory apparatus and its perceptual capabilities begin to limit it, so it is also important to pay attention to this issue.

Chapter 4. How do accordionists perceive their role in electroacoustic music?

Close collaboration and mutual understanding between composers and musicians are key to success in works for acoustic instrument with electronic layer. Such pieces are designed for the performer to play accompanied by electronic equipment. It's important, therefore, to understand the performer's perspective, their potential doubts, and individual interpretation of the composition. The goal is to create optimal working conditions for the musician, so they don't feel constrained or forced, allowing the piece to truly succeed. As both a composer myself and having composed numerous works of this kind, I conducted a survey among accordionists to learn about their experiences, perspectives on electroacoustic music, and to identify difficulties and ways to optimize the performance process.

The survey consisted of the following questions:

1. Please describe your experience in performing compositions for accordion with electronic layer (including both tape and live electronics) in one or two words. Whether it's extensive, limited, or none at all.
2. For those with experience in this field, please describe in one or two sentences how it has influenced your perception of music on the live instrument and the electronic layer. In other words, what were your expectations before your first performances of such compositions, and what is your current perspective? For those with little or no experience, please describe your expectations.
3. Please describe in two or three sentences (the response can be longer, depending on your preference) how performing music on a solo instrument (or with other acoustic instruments) differs from performing with an electronic layer. This includes technical aspects as well as the

perception of the sound of your own instrument and the experience of playing it. How does the use of electronic layer affect the perception of your own playing and the sound of your instrument?

4. Please briefly describe whether amplifying the instrument makes a significant difference compared to playing the instrument without amplification. How does it affect your approach to performing the piece and your perception of the sound of your instrument?
5. Please describe in one or two sentences the extent to which the need for precise timing, especially when playing with a click track in headphones, influences your approach to performing compositions with an electronic layer. Is it a hindrance or does it not matter much?

Many musicians responded to the survey, including those with extensive experience in this field, sporadic performers of electroacoustic repertoire, and beginners with only one or two attempts in this area. Importantly, responses came from musicians specializing in electroacoustic music as well as those performing a wide range of repertoire – solo, chamber, etc. Regarding the impact of these experiences on changing perceptions of music on live instruments and electronic layers, practically everyone noted the same thing – the necessity of greater focus, discipline, and precision in performance. Working with electronics made them hear their instrument differently, opening them up to entirely new possibilities. While some respondents see certain similarities between playing with electronics and playing with a live ensemble, they also note that electronics do not respond in the same way as live performers, so it's something different altogether. Generally, most survey participants emphasized that they didn't know what to expect before their first attempt at this kind of performance, but over time, they appreciated the discovery of a new world of sounds – virtually everyone was surprised by what they discovered for themselves. Some emphasized that the tight connection with electronics imposes certain limitations, but in return, they receive something unique that other music cannot offer. Here are a few excerpts from these responses:

"Electronics forced me to listen, to be precise, to concentrate harder. But it, in my opinion, opens up space. It gives freedom and the opportunity for exploration."

"In hindsight, the experience is not much different from performing chamber music with other instrumentalists, except that with electronic layer, you cannot rely on reactions to your playing and must strictly adhere to the tempo and composition plan."

"Playing with electronics opened me up to entirely new worlds. Playing without media at this point doesn't seem as interesting."

"Before performing, I had no idea how electronics worked, and during the rehearsal, I was surprised by its capabilities."

"Performing compositions with tape is a kind of enslavement for the performer. We follow the click track, time markers, or references noted in the score. On the other hand, this rhythmic or temporal discipline offers an interesting perception of us as performers. Limitation and distance become inspiring, leading to new ideas."

"I learned how electroacoustic music can create a new level of complexity and beauty."

"Experiences with electronics made me realize that preparing my part alone is not enough to succeed. It's important to thoroughly understand the electronic layer to properly adjust my performance techniques – articulation, register selection, dynamics. Additionally, there's the technique of reinforcing the accordion part to make it sound consistent with the electronic layer."

"Performing compositions for accordion and electronics made me aware of the importance of timing and synchronization between the performer and the electronic layer in such works. Another aspect turned out to be balancing the sound intensity of the live instrument and the sound coming from the

amplification equipment."

The responses to the question of how performing music on a solo instrument differs from music performed with an electronic layer were more diverse, showing individual approaches of each musician. Attention was drawn to what we deal with from the beginning, thus the difference in sound perception was the only common element, besides the statement that this kind of music fundamentally differs from others. The responses strongly reflected individual preferences; for some, the most fascinating aspect is the real-time processing of accordion sound, while for others, it's how amplification and the presence of electronics change the perception of their instrument. Let's quote a few excerpts:

"With tape, it's completely different. You can't pretend to be a soloist. We have to be much more precise – it's about timing, note duration. We also hear any imperfections, clicks, keyboard sounds, very clearly, as well as different tone because microphones, sound cards transfer frequencies differently."

"In the case of performing music with an electronic layer, the performer's perception depends on the method of amplification and playback of the electronic layer, which somewhat complicates and restricts the performer's freedom and control over the overall sound."

"Thanks to electronic layers, you can develop technique, improve sound quality. I see only advantages here."

"When I play other acoustic instruments, I hear them all precisely, but with live electronics, sometimes I miss that, as if the sound of my accordion and the electronic sound were perfectly merged."

"What fascinates me the most in performing music with electroacoustic layers is the execution and processing of accordion sound that is very coherent with the tape. The accordion then becomes one of the effects, an instrument whose sound often extends beyond its limits."

"The main issue with playing with tape is that you have to plan everything."

"Then there's the click track, helping to maintain contact with the electronic layer. The instrument sounds better thanks to amplification. Also, its imperfections – key clacks, buttons, registers – are more audible."

"In my opinion, the performer, during the execution of works with electronics, must ensure sound quality, which changes somewhat when the instrument is amplified. Precision in execution is extremely important in this case."

A more detailed question was whether amplifying the instrument makes a significant difference compared to playing the instrument without amplification. Here – except for one statement – there was complete agreement that it does, fundamentally. Amplification emphasizes certain elements, requires greater control over the sound, but also allows integration with the electronic layer. Let's support this with quotes again:

"I feel that with amplification, I can allow for louder dynamics, but with mezzo forte to forte, the accordion sounds quite sharp, so I try not to force the instrument. Accordionists tend to have uneven bellows control, and amplification emphasizes this issue."

"Amplification always changes the sound of the instrument. However, it's not always a problem. In this case, it all depends on how far-reaching changes are made to the sound and how much precision the composer expects in performance."

"In my opinion, it changes – if the microphones support it, you don't have to play with as much intensity as on an acoustic instrument. You can play a bit more delicately and achieve similar effects."

"I believe that mic'ing the accordion is necessary in many cases. Of course, it depends on the specific piece, but in most cases, the sound picked up by the microphones is used for electronic processing."

"It's a fact that we have to adjust our playing to different volume ranges provided by amplification."

"On one hand, there's joy that you can play so loudly, but on the other hand, there's awareness that it's easy to overdo it, to achieve a harsh sound."

"In my opinion, the perception of the instrument changes, as we become a sort of chamber musician with an electronic layer, with whom we must be consistent and in constant contact."

The last question concerned the impact of precise timing, especially playing with a click track in headphones – and in this case, the responses revealed strongly individual approaches of the respondents. It's evident that some musicians enjoy playing with a click track, finding it helpful and not limiting, while for others, it's a hindrance and distracts their attention from other aspects of performance. However, generally, everyone agrees that in certain situations, it's necessary, although it's often seen as a necessary evil. Let's quote excerpts from a few responses:

"It's an absolutely essential skill, the lack of which causes a lot of performance problems if not practiced. Timing is crucial!"

"Playing with a click track in headphones is a challenge for the instrumentalist. It forces extra focus and concentration not only on sound and interpretation but also on controlling the metronome. Unfortunately, it limits performance freedom."

"It all depends on what's easier for the performer and what the composer wants to achieve. The click is quite a comfortable medium. You don't have to listen so much to the electronics or partner, in case the piece involves multiple instruments."

"Playing with a metronome organizes the performance but doesn't provide full freedom. The downside of playing with a click is that as a performer of the entire sonic palette of the composition, I'm often rushed by the click."

"It depends on the type of music we play, but rhythmic pieces require excellent planning and precise perspective."

"It's quite a challenge because it enforces mathematical precision. A live co-performer can adjust. On the other hand, the click allows for precise performance of most pieces that would be played haphazardly without it."

"Maintaining timing while performing a piece with a click track in headphones isn't of great importance to me, but in my opinion, it determines the necessity of preparing the piece with a metronome from the very beginning. It facilitates synchronization with the electronic layer later on."

Chapter 5. Conclusion

As evident from the extensive discussion on the perception of sound in musical compositions, especially those involving acoustic instruments and electronic layers, it is a matter of utmost importance. This perception is crucial not only for the composers but also for the listeners who seek to engage with works that provide them with unparalleled experiences on every level. However, to achieve this, it requires multidimensional and meticulous consideration from the composer, encompassing not only aesthetic but also technical aspects. Understanding that creating comfortable conditions for the

instrumentalist is crucial for the ultimate success of the piece is immensely important. While a composition may be theoretically well-written, if the composer fails to plan it in a way that makes it an inspiring challenge for the musician and, bluntly put, playable according to the intentions, the end result will be a failure. As a composer creating both strictly electroacoustic, acousmatic music, and compositions for instruments with electronics, I know that similar creators sometimes struggle to understand that a live musician is not an apparatus that will do everything in any conditions. The musician must comprehend the meaning and intention of the work, their role – they must accept it and recognize that they have something interesting to present. They must have the chance to hear themselves, feel their instrument at all times, and have full control over their performance. Therefore, dialogue, listening to the needs and expectations of the performer is crucial. On one hand, one must stand their ground, but on the other, one cannot impose something on the musician that goes against their will, experience, and preferences. We should not insist on specific technical solutions if the performer suggests others that suit them better while achieving the same effect.

For musicians, the perception of sound during the performance of an electroacoustic piece is very important, as the survey showed. All respondents acknowledge that even just amplification changes this perception, and the electronic layer is an additional element influencing the sound perception. It's something entirely different from performing an acoustic composition without amplification. While amplification itself is not a problem for musicians, it's different with the click track, which is often seen as a hindrance and limitation, although in many cases, it's also a tool that helps maintain performance discipline. Regardless of individual approaches and preferences, everyone emphasizes that playing with electronics is a new and inspiring experience.

Reflections on the perception of sound may seem somewhat academic and outside the main area of interest for composers or musicians. However, in the case of music involving electronic means, it is a matter of paramount importance. Therefore, it is worth paying attention to it, familiarizing oneself with the basic issues, and drawing practical conclusions from it.

Author

Dariusz Mazurowski – a Polish composer of electroacoustic music, producer, and performer based in Gdańsk. He creates acousmatic works, compositions for instruments and electronics, as well as projects in the field of sound installations and improvised electroacoustic music. In his artistic practice, he combines analog instrumentation and self-designed electronic constructions with digital technology, employing, among other techniques, live electronics, multichannel sound diffusion, and methods of processing and transforming concrete sound material.

His works have been presented at numerous international electroacoustic music festivals across Europe, the Americas, and Asia, and have been broadcast by radio stations worldwide. He is the author of publications devoted to contemporary music and technological issues, a participant in academic conferences and workshops, and an active member of the Polish Society for Electroacoustic Music (PSeME).

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